

Spectroscopic long-term monitoring of RZ Cas

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Abstract

RZ Cas is an active, short-period Algol-type system where the primary component shows Delta Scuti-like pulsations. We investigate hundreds of high-resolution spectra taken with the 2-m telescope of the Thüringer Landessternwarte Tautenburg and with the HERMES spectrograph at the Mercator Telescope at La Palma over a time span of 16 years. We use a newly developed program package to analyse the radial velocity (RV) and line profile variations (LPV). Main tasks are to disentangle the line profiles and RVs of the components as well as pulsation from orbital motion. The main goal is to correlate the variations of orbital period, $v \sin i$ or differential rotation, and the occurrence, amplitudes, and frequencies of different pulsation modes with each other and with the occurrence of episodes of rapid mass transfer. Preliminary results are presented.

1 Introduction

RZ Cas belongs to the *oscillating Eclipsing Algol-type (oEA) stars*. This group of stars was defined in the early 2000s (Mkrтчichian *et al.*, 2002) as active, semi-detached, eclipsing binaries of Algol-type, in which the mass-accreting primary is a A–F type main sequence star that shows δ Sct-like pulsations. Research on stars of this class is interesting, for at least three reasons. First, due to the ongoing mass transfer, it is possible to study stellar evolution on short timescales. Second, because of the observed changes in oscillation patterns, the changes in the outer layers of the mass gaining primary can be investigated asteroseismologically. And third, principles of the interaction between the magnetic activity cycle of the mass-losing secondary, the episodes of mass transfer and the excitation of pulsation modes in the primary can be inferred (Tkachenko *et al.*, 2009).

Being a bright ($V=6.26$) star, RZ Cas has been studied for a long time. Its light-curves and radial velocities (RVs) with complex structures point towards a complex distribution of circumstellar/-binary matter, a hot spot on the primary and a dark one on the secondary, and a gas stream transferring matter from secondary to primary component (e.g. Lehmann & Mkrтчichian, 2004; Tkachenko *et al.*, 2009, and references therein). Its spectral type is A3 V + K0 IV and it is a short period ($P \sim 1.19526$ d) binary. Spectroscopic measurements revealed a different behaviour between a transient episode of stronger mass transfer in 2001 and a quiet phase in 2006. This concerns changes in orbital period, pulsation patterns, and distribution of circumstellar material (Lehmann & Mkrтчichian, 2008; Tkachenko *et al.*, 2009). Analogue findings are known from photometry taken over decades (Mkrтчichian *et al.*, 2018).

In our project, we investigate hundreds (see Tab. 1) of

high-resolution spectra taken with the 2-m telescope of the Thüringer Landessternwarte Tautenburg and with the HERMES spectrograph at the Mercator Telescope at La Palma over a time span of 16 years. Our main goal is to correlate the variations of orbital period, $v \sin i$ or differential rotation, and the occurrence, amplitudes, and frequencies of different pulsation modes with each other and with the occurrence of episodes of rapid mass transfer.

Here, we present two newly developed methods and preliminary results of their application to our data. First, LSDbinary, which is a new approach to the classical Least-Squares Deconvolution (LSD) method. Further, a Python-based extension to the pixel-by-pixel method of the FAMIAS program (Zima, 2008) which adds the functionality of an automated frequency search as well as a fit function that allows to also optimise the frequencies and therefore to calculate uncertainties for them.

2 LSDbinary

SB2 stars in eclipsing binaries provide the clue to the determination of important stellar parameters like absolute masses and effective temperatures. For absolute masses, we need to derive the RVs of the components. For spectrum and line profile analysis, we first need to disentangle the observed composite spectra to obtain the spectra of the components. For semi-detached binaries like the Algol-type ones, the analysis is complicated by the non-spherical shape of the stars and non-Keplerian effects in orbital motion.

Using information from many lines in a stellar spectrum to construct an averaged line profile of high S/N is the idea behind the Least-Squares Deconvolution (LSD) technique that was developed by Donati & Collier Cameron (1997) for research on magnetic polarization features in stellar spectra. Applying this technique to composite spectra of SB2 stars and to calculate fully separated LSD profiles of the components is the aim of *LSDbinary*, a method developed by Tsymbal *et al.* (2019). As in the classical approach, the method is based on line masks but it uses two different masks for the two stars, corresponding to their spectral types. Synthetic spectra are used to determine the deviations caused by the underlying simplifications like assuming identical line profiles and linear addition in blends and to apply correspond-

Table 1: Number of observations per epoch used for oscillation frequencies search. BJD gives the mean BJD 2450000+.

year	2001	2006	2008	2009	2013	2014	2015	2016
BJD	2192	3768	4717	5156	6635	6936	7278	7646
number	743	465	54	166	653	631	804	468

Figure 1: LSD profiles of primary (left) and secondary (right) component of RZ Cas from spectra taken during primary eclipse around zero orbital phase.

Figure 2: RVs of primary and secondary component of RZ Cas measured in 2013 (black dots) and fitted using PHOEBE (solid lines) with (green) and without (blue) assuming a cool spot on the secondary component.

ing corrections. Also the continuum flux ratio between the two stars is included into the calculations, which is an important issue in the case of Algol-type stars having components of very different spectral type and brightness. Furthermore, guess values of the RVs of the components have to be provided. By folding the computed LSD profiles with the corresponding line masks, the program is able to perform spectrum decomposition on single composite spectra. Details on implementation and mathematical background will be given in an upcoming paper. Here, we focus on presenting preliminary results of the application of this tool to spectra of the oEA star RZ Cas.

The main output of the calculations in our case are the separated LSD profiles for primary and secondary component (Fig. 1) as well as precise RVs (Fig. 2). As can be seen from Fig. 1, the line profiles do not only shift according to orbital motion but the profiles of the primary component also change their shapes due to the Rossiter-McLaughlin effect (RME) during primary eclipse. As will be described in Sect. 4, the calculated profiles also show the impact of stellar pulsations and, probably, of stellar spots.

Figure 3: Orbital period changes of RZ Cas obtained from the RVs (see text). Changes compared to the mean period over all epochs are given.

Figure 4: RV residuals versus out-of-eclipse phases, when assuming one common orbital period (black) or different periods in different epochs (red).

Figure 2 shows the calculated RVs for spectra measured in 2013 and simulated RV curves, calculated with the PHOEBE program, assuming/not assuming a spot on the secondary. Obviously, the RVs of the primary component are very precise and follow the course expected from Keplerian motion and RME. Also, stellar pulsation has an imprint on the measured RVs and LSD profiles of the primary, as we show in Sections 4 and 5. Due to the lower brightness of the companion, the secondary RVs scatter more, but are much more precise compared to those obtained with our implementation of the two-dimensional cross-correlation program TODCOR (Zucker & Mazeh, 1994). The main problem in analysis with PHOEBE here is the non-spherical shape and the occurrence of a cool spot on the secondary component as already stated in Tkachenko *et al.* (2009) from the observations in 2006. That is why all the results here, that are based on the PHOEBE solutions, are preliminary results.

3 Period changes

We used the RVs derived from different epochs to look for changes in the orbital period of RZ Cas. The time coverage of the RVs from single epochs was not sufficient to find differences between different epochs, however. That is why we used the RVs from pairs of neighbouring epochs which are separated by one year or more. In this way we calculated the orbital parameters for the mean BJD of each pair, allowing for a linear change of the orbital period and extrapolated the period values to the mean BJD of the single epochs.

Figure 3 shows the results. The values of period change extrapolated from neighbouring pairs of epochs agree well. Figure 4 compares the O–C residuals obtained from a common solution, based on a period that fits the RVs from all epochs best, with the residuals obtained when calculating different periods for different epochs as described before. In the latter case, the sum of squares is reduced by 50%.

4 Automated search for LPV frequencies

We applied the pixel-by-pixel method of the FAMIAS program (Zima, 2008) to search for short-term oscillations in the computed LSD profiles of the primary component of RZ Cas. This method also allows to detect high-degree l -modes from LPV. We only used profiles taken out of primary eclipse and shifted them in RV according to the derived orbital solutions.

The FAMIAS program works in a two-staged process and is illustrated in Fig. 5. First, a two-dimensional Fourier spectrum is computed by calculating one-dimensional spectra for every dispersion bin of a time series of profiles (see upper panel) and then the mean Fourier spectrum for all bins (red line in the lower panel). The frequency at the maximum peak of this mean Fourier spectrum is then taken as the first found frequency. The second step is a least-squares fit followed by pre-whitening of the data. Every bin is fitted individually by the sum of determined frequency contributions where the amplitudes and phases are re-determined but the frequencies are kept at the values determined in the first step. After fitting, each individual model is subtracted from its corresponding bin and the procedure begins anew with the residuals as input data (see blue line in the lower panel of Fig. 5, which is the mean Fourier spectrum after subtracting the first frequency).

This procedure has two main disadvantages. First, it requires an enormous effort in interactive work with the FAMIAS GUI when dealing with many frequencies. Secondly, as the least-squares fit of the pixel-by-pixel method does no frequency optimisation, no frequency errors can be estimated. But uncertainty estimations for the frequencies are necessary, if significant changes in the frequency pattern between different epochs shall be monitored.

We developed a Python based extension to the FAMIAS program, which tackles both of these issues. First, it performs a fully automated frequency search based on the priorly described procedure. However, after finding a new frequency, this frequency is added and all other frequencies found so far are checked for their values and significance again, where we use significance criteria similar to the $S/N > 4$ criterion from Breger *et al.* (1993). The second step is a least-squares fit to the data that also optimises the frequencies. Contrary to FAMIAS, we are not fitting the bins individually but altogether in one fit which was made possible due to a careful construction of the vector of residuals and the Jacobian matrix. The uncertainties of the frequencies are then calculated from the correlation matrix of the fit. For further details we refer to an upcoming paper.

The application to our data set yielded two groups of frequencies (see Fig. 5): There are low frequencies extending up to about 15 cd^{-1} and a group in the high-frequency domain between about $55\text{--}75 \text{ cd}^{-1}$. The latter is shown in Fig. 6 as found with our automated search in different years of observation. The size of the diamonds correspond to the amplitude integrated over the profile.

The five frequencies found in the high-frequency domain are $f_1 = 62.4 \text{ cd}^{-1}$, $f_2 = 64.2 \text{ cd}^{-1}$, $f_3 = 64.9 \text{ cd}^{-1}$, $f_4 = 65.6 \text{ cd}^{-1}$, and $f_5 = 70.2 \text{ cd}^{-1}$ (mean values). All frequencies and corresponding amplitudes show timely variations. The separation of the ‘triplet’ f_2, f_3, f_4 (Fig. 7) is 0.71 cd^{-1} corresponding to a period of 1.41 d, which is distinctly larger than the orbital period of 1.19526 d.

In the low-frequency regime, we found the peaks with highest amplitudes very close to the orbital frequency and its multiples (up to five harmonics). We suspect that they might come from spots on the primary or from circumprimary/-binary material. At present stage, also an imperfect subtrac-

Figure 5: *Top*: 2D-Fourier spectrum of a group of LSD profiles from 2006. Brighter colors correspond to higher amplitude. Each line corresponds to a single dispersion bin. *Bottom*: Fourier spectra of the corresponding individual bins (gray), mean spectrum (red), and mean spectrum after subtracting the frequency (70.3067 cd^{-1}) with the highest peak in the red spectrum (blue).

Figure 6: Preliminary results of the frequency search in LPV in the high-frequency regime. Sizes of the diamonds correspond to their integrated amplitude.

Figure 7: Zoom into Fig. 6 showing $f_2, f_3,$ and f_4 with error bars.

Figure 8: Values of $v \sin i$ versus out-of-eclipse phases, measured from the LSD profiles observed in 2016 (black) and from the same profiles corrected for low-frequency variations (red).

tion of orbital motion cannot be excluded.

5 Rotation velocity

We used the Fourier method (see e.g. Smith & Gray, 1976) to measure $v \sin i$ from the LSD profiles. Depending on the S/N of the spectra, we could determine two to four stellar rotation related zero points in the Fourier power spectra. Figure 8 shows the resulting $v \sin i$ values for one epoch as an example. A strong variation with orbital phase can be seen. We assume that this variation comes from Algol-typical effects like inhomogeneous circumprimary environment and surface structure caused by the influence of mass transfer and gas stream from the secondary component. To derive cleaned $v \sin i$, we removed all the low-frequency variations found in the LSD profiles (see Sect. 4) by subtracting them pixel-by-pixel from each profile. The resulting $v \sin i$ are shown in red color. The distribution is very flat and we used it to calculate the $v \sin i$ of the corresponding epoch from the arithmetic mean. Results are shown in Fig. 9.

6 Conclusions

The LSDbinary program, firstly tested on the short period eclipsing binary RCMa (Lehmann *et al.*, 2018), delivers RVs and LSD profiles of high accuracy also for the components of RZ Cas. From previous spectroscopic investigations (Lehmann & Mkrichian, 2008; Tkachenko *et al.*, 2009), we can reason that the star was in an active phase with enhanced mass transfer rate close to 2001 and in a relatively quiet state in 2006. The period changes derived from the RVs of the primary component as well as its $v \sin i$ values also point to an extraordinary event covered by the observations in 2001. The $v \sin i$ is distinctly higher than in the following epochs and the orbital period drops down by 2.7 ± 0.4 sec after 2001. The latter is in agreement with the finding in Tkachenko *et al.* (2009) where a period change by 2.9 ± 1.7 sec was stated. After 2005, there is either a continuous rise of orbital period until 2015 or a quasi-periodic change with one further maximum around 2011-2012, unfortunately not covered by our observations. Such a quasi-periodic behaviour, triggered by the magnetic activity cycle of the cool companion, was suspected by Mkrichian *et al.* (2018). From the O-C data of times of minimum authors derive possible periods of 4.8, 6.1, and 9.2 years. The 9.2 years period would be compatible with a second maximum in orbital period occurring during the above mentioned gap in our observations. For the $v \sin i$, the distribution after 2001 is flat but also a second maximum cannot be excluded.

The determination of pulsation frequencies and amplitudes requires a careful separation of oscillations due to pul-

Figure 9: Mean values of $v \sin i$ derived from different epochs of observation.

sation from changes due to orbital motion (RV) and eclipses (LPV and RV). The main problem in determining the orbital solution from the RVs is actually the presence of spots on the stellar surfaces that strongly influences the determination of separation, mass ratio, and masses of the components. A cool, spot-like region on the companion pointing towards the primary component was already found in Tkachenko *et al.* (2009). Also a hot spot on the primary has an impact on the RVs, modifying them in orbital phases $-0.1..0.0$, i.e. during the ingress of primary eclipse. PHOEBE assumes Roche geometry of the components and thus handles the non-spherical shape of the companion well. We are about to also include spots into our model using PHOEBE scripiter, trying to optimize their parameters and finally to derive accurate orbital solutions.

Because of the mentioned problems, we here only show a qualitative picture of the pulsational behaviour of RZ Cas. We see from Fig. 6 that different pulsation modes are excited in different epochs. Moreover, mode amplitudes and frequencies change. Modes f_2 and f_4 are present in most of the epochs. f_2 is well-known from photometry. It was the dominating mode in 1997 (Ohshima *et al.*, 1998), 1999 (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2002), and 2001 (Mkrichian *et al.*, 2003) and is most probably a sectorial $l=2$, $m=-1$ mode as it was shown by Mkrichian *et al.* (2018). Also f_1 was found in the photometric data, e.g. in 1997 (Ohshima *et al.*, 2001), 1999 (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2004), or 2003 (Mkrichian *et al.*, 2018). There is one further frequency of 56.6 cd^{-1} found in several epochs in photometry (see Mkrichian *et al.*, 2018, for a comprehensive overview). It was also detected in our RVs from 2001 and 2006 (Lehmann & Mkrichian, 2004, 2008) but could not be found from the LPV analysis. Instead, we detect three completely new frequencies, namely f_3 , f_4 and f_5 . Moreover, the amplitude of f_4 or f_5 dominates the LPV variations in some of the years (see Fig. 6).

Complete and improved results on orbital solutions, derived stellar parameters, pulsation frequencies and mode identification will be presented in a forthcoming paper.

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